

Microwave assisted synthesis of some thiazolyl-pyrazoline and *N*-phenyl-2-pyrazoline derivatives over potassium carbonate

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Abstract : In the present study, a series of twenty new *N*-(1,5-diphenyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-3-pyrazolyl)-*N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)amine (**4a-j**) and *N*-(5-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-3-pyrazolyl)-*N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)amine (**5a-j**) have been synthesized in 70–85% yield by a microwave-assisted solvent-free condensation of *N*1-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)-(Z)-3-phenyl-2-propenamide (**3a-j**) with hydrazine hydrate/*N*-phenylhydrazine in ethanol over potassium carbonate. The reaction condition is simple, involves the treatment of ice-cold water and eliminates the usage of solvent. The reaction time is minimizes from hours to minutes with increase in yield.

Keywords : Pyrazoline, thiazole, microwave irradiation, solvent-free synthesis.

Introduction

Different substituted pyrazolines and their derivatives have been reported as a broad spectrum of biological activities such as antitumor¹, antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anti-invasive, antiparasitic, anti-tubercular, insecticidal agents²⁻¹¹ and also anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anaesthetic and analgesic properties¹²⁻¹⁵. Moreover, the pyrazoline molecule is relatively stable, and has attracted medicinal chemists to exploit this stable moiety to synthesize new scaffolds, as evident from the literature¹⁶⁻²⁷. Thiazole moiety has already been reported for variety of biological properties²⁸ such as antimicrobial activity²⁹. This prompted us to synthesize various substituted thiazolyl chalcones and clubbed with pyrazoline using the microwave-assisted method. In recent years, the use of microwave-assisted Organic Reaction Enhancement (MORE) chemistry have a environmentally benign synthetic methods gained considerable attention as non-conventional technique for rapid organic synthesis and solvent-free protocols are reported³⁰⁻³². A fast, highly efficient and eco-friendly solvent-free chemical transformation, for the synthesis of title compounds, under microwave irradiation, using potassium carbonate and basic alumina is designed. Thus we herein reports synthesis of the title compounds using MAOS.

Results and discussion

Compounds **1** and **2** were synthesized as per the literature^{33,34}. Usually the desired chalcones (**3a-j**) were synthesized by reacting *N*1-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)acetamide (**2**) with different substituted aromatic aldehydes in the presence of NaOH, KOH or Ba(OH)₂. In a typical case, equimolar quantities of chalcones (**3a-j**) and hydrazine hydrate/*N*-phenylhydrazine were adsorbed over K₂CO₃ (Method A) and subjected to MWI, which lead to the formation of pyrazolines (**4a-j**) and *N*-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (**5a-j**) (Scheme 1). For a comparative study the reactants were adsorbed on basic alumina (Method B) and irradiated in a microwave oven. The effects of microwave irradiation time on the reaction were studied and the results are summarized in Table 1. The elution of product from 1 g reaction batch, with basic alumina requires about 30–35 ml of acetone, whereas with K₂CO₃ only water is required. This eliminates the use of organic solvent from the reaction. The reaction time has minimized from hours to minutes with enhanced yields using MWI. However, the yields of both methods (A and B) are equally satisfactory. Lower yields were obtained under conventional method (47%) as compared to microwave irradiation (82%), representing that the effect of microwave irradiation is not purely thermal. All these

Table 1. Microwave-assisted K₂CO₃/basic alumina mediated synthesis of 4a-j and 5a-j

Compd.	R	Conventional heating (h)	Method A/K ₂ CO ₃		Method B/Basic alumina	
			Time (min)	Yield ^a (%)	Time (min)	Yield ^a (%)
4a	C ₆ H ₅	2	15	70	7	75
4b	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2	13.5	80	7.5	81
4c	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2	12	85	7	85
4d	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	2	13	82	7	84
4e	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	2	12.5	83	7.5	80
4f	4-OHC ₆ H ₄	2	15	75	7	75
4g	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	2	13.5	78	7.5	81
4h	4-CH ₃	2	13.5	82	7.5	72
4i	4-Cl	2	15	74	7	76
4j	2-Cl	2	12	81	7	81
5a	C ₆ H ₅	5	10	80	6.5	80
5b	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	5	9	83	6	80
5c	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	5	9.5	85	6.5	82
5d	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	5	10	78	6	81
5e	3,4,5-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	5	9.5	82	5.5	70
5f	4-OHC ₆ H ₄	5	9.5	81	6.5	81
5g	4-BrC ₆ H ₄	5	8.5	70	5.5	74
5h	4-CH ₃	5	10	72	6	70
5i	4-Cl	5	9	82	6	82
5j	2-Cl	5	9.5	80	6.5	84

^aYield of isolated products.

products were characterized on the basis of the IR, ¹H NMR and elemental analysis. The IR spectra of condensed products displayed disappearance of band at 1650–1660 cm⁻¹ due to C=O of chalcones and appearance of a band at 1580–1640 cm⁻¹. The ¹H NMR spectra of compounds showed characteristic signals corresponding to protons at C₄ and C₅ of pyrazoline ring system. Microwave irradiation facilitates the polarization of the molecules, causing rapid reaction to occur. When the resultant chalcones and hydrazine hydrate/*N*-phenylhydrazine were subjected to microwave irradiation over K₂CO₃ (20%) of the starting material was recovered. The same reaction with conventional methods gave 45% of the product, and 40% of the starting material was recovered.

Antimicrobial activity : From the antibacterial screening it was observed that all the compounds exhibited activity against all the organisms employed. Looking at the structure-activity relationship, marked inhibition in bacteria was observed in the compounds 4e, 4f, 4g, 5e, 5f and 5g whereas 4a, 4b, 4c, 4d, 4h, 5a, 5b, 5c, 5d and 5h

have shown moderate activity and others showed least activity.

Experimental

Chemistry :

The melting points were recorded on electrothermal apparatus and are uncorrected. The purities of the compounds were checked on silica-gel-coated Al plates (Merck). IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer model-983. ¹H NMR spectrum recorded on Varian Mercury 300 MHz instrument using CDCl₃, DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent (chemical shift in δ ppm), using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on a Finning LCQ mass spectrometer. Microwave irradiation was carried out in Raga Scientific Microwave Systems; Model RG31L at 2450 MHz. Elemental analysis was performed on a Heracus CHN analyzer. Analyses indicated by the symbols of the elements of functions were within ±0.4% of the theoretical values.

The preparation of compound 4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-

amine (1) was synthesized as per reported procedure³³, the compound *N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)acetamide (2) was synthesized as per literature procedure³⁴. Chalcone (3a-j) derivatives were synthesized by condensing *N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)acetamide (2) with various aldehydes according to the method reported in the literature^{34,35}. Synthetic routes of the newly synthesized compounds are depicted in Scheme 1.

Microwave/K₂CO₃ mediated synthesis of pyrazolines (4a-j) and N-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (5a-j) (Method A) :

A mixture of the chalcone (3a-j) (2.2 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate/*N*-phenylhydrazine (2 mmol) was dissolved in acetone (5 mL) and ethanol (5 mL), then K₂CO₃ (4.0 g) was added and stirred vigorously. After 5 min, the solvent was removed under vacuum and the dry powder was irradiated in a microwave oven for the appropriate time (Table) at 650 W. The completion of reaction was examined by TLC (ethanol : ethyl acetate, 4 : 1); ice-cold water was added to the reaction mixture. In all cases the products obtained showed single spot on TLC plate. The solid product was obtained, which was filtered, dried and crystallized from a suitable solvent (hot ethanol).

Microwave/basic-alumina-mediated synthesis of pyrazolines (4a-j) and N-phenyl-2-pyrazoline (5a-j) (Method B) :

A mixture of the chalcone (3a-j) (2.2 mmol) and hydrazine hydrate/*N*-phenylhydrazine (2 mmol) was dissolved in acetone (5 mL) and ethanol (5 mL) respectively. Basic alumina (4 g; aluminium oxide, basic, Brockmann I, ca. 150 mesh, 58 Å CAMAG 506-C-I, surface area 155 m²/g, pH 80) was added and stirred vigorously. After 5 min, the solvent was removed under vacuum and the dry powder was irradiated in a microwave oven for the appropriate time (Table) at 650 W. After completion of the reaction followed by TLC (ethanol : ethyl acetate, 4 : 1) the product was eluted with acetone (30 mL). In all cases the products obtained showed single spot on TLC plate. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure yielded the product which was recrystallized from hot ethanol.

Spectral data :

N-(5-Phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-3-pyrazolyl)-*N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)amine (4a) : m.p. 155 °C; IR (KBr) : 3249, 1590, 1545, 1532, 1340 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.08 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.29 (1H, dd, Hb), 5.48 (1H, dd, Hc), 4.90 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 4.00 (1H, s, NH), 7.05 (1H, s, NH-pyrazoline), 7.10–7.80

(10H, m, ArH); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 320 (100) [M⁺], 321 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₆N₄S : C, 67.47; H, 5.03; N, 17.49. Found : C, 67.40; H, 5.05; N, 17.38.

N-[5-(2-Nitrophenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-3-pyrazolyl]-*N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)amine (4b) : m.p. 165 °C; IR (KBr) : 3258, 1590, 1578, 1548 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.10 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.30 (1H, dd, Hb), 5.50 (1H, dd, Hc), 4.91 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 4.00 (1H, s, NH), 7.08 (1H, s, NH-pyrazoline), 7.13–7.82 (9H, m, ArH); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 365 (100) [M⁺], 366 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₅N₅O₂S : C, 59.16; H, 4.14; N, 19.17. Found : C, 59.10; H, 4.12; N, 19.10.

*N*2-5-[4-(Dimethylamino)phenyl]-4,5-dihydro-1H-3-pyrazolyl-4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-amine (4c) : m.p. 167 °C; IR (KBr) : 3264, 1560, 1546, 1526, 1340 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.85 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.25 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.90 (1H, dd, Hb), 5.48 (1H, dd, Hc), 4.95 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 4.01 (1H, s, NH), 7.81 (1H, s, NH-pyrazoline), 6.51–7.55 (9H, m, ArH); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 363 (100) [M⁺], 364 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₂₁N₅S : C, 66.09; H, 5.82; N, 19.27. Found : C, 66.07; H, 5.78; N, 19.21.

N-[5-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-3-pyrazolyl]-*N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)amine (4d) : m.p. 150 °C; IR (KBr) : 3254, 2830, 1730, 1560, 1538 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.12 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.33 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.80 (1H, dd, Hb), 5.55 (1H, dd, Hc), 4.95 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 4.05 (1H, s, NH), 7.61 (1H, s, NH-pyrazoline), 7.00–7.53 (9H, m, ArH); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 350 (100) [M⁺], 351 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₄OS : C, 65.12; H, 5.18; N, 15.99. Found : C, 65.07; H, 5.12; N, 15.90.

4,3-[4-Phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl]amino]-4,5-dihydro-1H-5-pyrazolylphenol (4f) : m.p. 145 °C; IR (KBr) : 3340, 1650, 1560, 1340 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.38 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.58 (1H, dd, Hb), 4.98 (1H, dd, Hc), 9.01 (1H, br. s, OH), 4.95 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 4.01 (1H, s, NH), 7.65 (1H, s, NH-pyrazoline), 6.65–7.55 (9H, m, ArH); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 336 (100) [M⁺], 337 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₆N₄OS : C, 64.26; H, 4.79; N, 16.65. Found : C, 64.21; H, 4.75; N, 16.60.

N-(1,5-Diphenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-3-pyrazolyl)-*N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)amine (5a) : m.p. 235 °C; IR (KBr) : 3340, 1620, 1590, 1340, 619 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR

(300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.32 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.85 (1H, dd, Hb), 5.18 (1H, dd, Hc), 4.95 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 9.01 (1H, br. s, NH), 6.51–7.80 (14H, m, ArH); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 396 (100) [M⁺], 397 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₀N₄S : C, 72.70; H, 5.08; N, 14.13. Found : C, 72.66; H, 5.05; N, 14.15.

N-[5-(2-Nitrophenyl)-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-3-pyrazolyl]-*N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)amino (**5b**) : m.p. 230 °C; IR (KBr) : 3390, 1620, 1590, 1533, 617 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.08 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.90 (1H, dd, Hb), 5.63 (1H, dd, Hc), 4.95 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 9.01 (1H, br. s, NH), 7.12–8.18 (14H, m, ArH); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 441 (100) [M⁺], 442 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₉N₅O₂S : C, 65.29; H, 4.34; N, 15.86. Found : C, 65.25; H, 4.30; N, 15.82.

*N*2-5-[4-(Dimethylamino)phenyl]-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-3-pyrazolyl-4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-amine (**5c**) : m.p. 260 °C; IR (KBr) : 3365, 2875, 1620, 1590, 1440, 613 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 2.86 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 3.48 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.95 (1H, dd, Hb), 5.68 (1H, dd, Hc), 4.91 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 9.00 (1H, br. s, NH), 6.72–7.58 (14H, m, ArH); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 439 (100) [M⁺], 440 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₅N₅S : C, 71.04; H, 5.73; N, 15.93. Found : C, 71.00; H, 5.75; N, 15.95.

N-[5-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-3-pyrazolyl]-*N*-(4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)amine (**5d**) : m.p. 145 °C; IR (KBr) : 3340, 1600, 1590, 1340, 615 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.25 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.61 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.82 (1H, dd, Hb), 5.24 (1H, dd, Hc), 4.95 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 8.95 (1H, br. s, NH), 7.02–7.55 (14H, m, ArH), MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 426 (100) [M⁺], 427 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₅H₂₂N₄OS : C, 70.40; H, 5.20; N, 13.14. Found : C, 70.35; H, 5.15; N, 13.15.

N-(4-Phenyl-1,3-thiazol-2-yl)-*N*-[1-phenyl-5-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-3-pyrazolyl]amine (**5e**) : m.p. 145 °C; IR (KBr) : 3283, 2970, 1660, 1590, 619 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃-DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 3.18 (1H, dd, Ha), 3.81 (9H, s, OCH₃), 3.95 (1H, dd, Hb), 5.88 (1H, dd, Hc), 4.95 (1H, s, CH-thiazole), 8.98 (1H, br. s, NH), 6.72–7.55 (12H, m, ArH); MS (EI) : *m/z* (%) 486 (100) [M⁺], 487 [M+1]; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₇H₂₆N₄O₃S : C, 66.65; H, 5.39; N, 11.51. Found : C, 66.61; H, 5.35; N, 11.45.

Antimicrobial activity : The compounds listed in Table 1 were screened for the antimicrobial activity against different microorganisms under the following conditions.

Method : Well diffusion method³⁶, Medium : the nutrient agar medium, Solvent : chloroform, Concentrations : 50 μ M and 100 μ M, Condition : 24 h at 24–28 °C, Standard : the antibiotic gentamycin.

The nutrient agar medium, 20 mL, was poured into the sterile petri dishes. To the solidified plates, wells were made using a sterile cork borer 10 mm in diameter. The 24-hour subcultured bacteria were inoculated in the petri-plates, with a sterile cotton swab dipped in the nutrient broth medium. After inoculating, the compounds were dissolved separately with the chloroform solvent and poured into the wells with varying concentrations ranging from 50 to 100 μ M using a micropipette. The plates were left over for 24 h at 24–28 °C. The antibiotic gentamycin was used as a standard for comparative study (Table 2).

Table 2. Antibacterial activity of the compounds 4a-j and 5a-j

Compd.	Organisms			
	S.a.	P.a.	E.c.	S.t.
4a	24	19	19	17
4b	25	20	20	20
4c	21	24	23	21
4d	22	27	18	22
4e	31	30	26	25
4f	30	31	24	26
4g	32	30	25	24
4h	30	32	26	27
4i	27	20	22	20
4j	28	21	23	18
5a	26	19	20	19
5b	21	24	19	23
5c	20	26	18	21
5d	18	13	21	18
5e	24	27	20	19
5f	26	28	17	18
5g	24	26	24	24
5h	30	32	26	27
5i	27	20	22	20
5j	28	21	23	18
Gentamycin	34	35	31	30

S.a. *Staphylococcus aureus*, E.c. *Escherichia coli*, P.a. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, S.t. *Salmonella typhosa*.

The percentage of inhibition was calculated by the formula :

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} =$$

$$\frac{\text{Diameter of the inhibition zone} \times 100}{\text{Diameter of the well}}$$

Conclusion :

In conclusion, this work demonstrates a rapid, simple, convenient and efficient environmentally friendly synthetic methodology for pyrazoline derivatives using microwave assisted solvent-free reaction. The results obtained confirm the superiority of the microwave irradiation method over the classical heating one. The structure activity relationship suggested that fused pyrazoline containing 3,4,5-(OCH₃)₂C₆H₄, 4-OHC₆H₄, 4-BrC₆H₄ and C₆H₅, 4-OCH₃-C₆H₄, NO₂C₆H₄, 4-N(CH₃)₂C₆H₄ showed higher antibacterial activity than the corresponding other moieties. These findings encourage us to explore other molecules by introducing these potent moieties into other fused heterocycles. Our prediction is that these compounds with new ring systems may show even better antimicrobial activities.

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